

Evaluation of Diluted and Distance Education Practices According to Teacher Opinions in the Context of Inclusive Education

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ABSTRACT: In this study, it is aimed to evaluate the diluted and distance education practices at the primary school level in Turkey in the context of inclusive education according to teachers' views. This study, which was designed with qualitative research method, is a phenomenology study. The study group consists of seven primary school teachers working in Gaziantep province in the 2020-2021 academic years. The study group was formed by criterion sampling method, one of the purposeful sampling types. A semi-structured interview form developed by the researchers was used in the study. The data obtained from the study were analysed by content analysis method. Ethics committee permission was obtained prior to the study and ethical principles were followed throughout the study. In the study, it was found that teachers preferred to create a homogeneous classroom environment while dividing the class into two groups in diluted education practices. The teachers who participated in the study stated that they used demonstration, question-answer, lecture and problem solving methods and techniques respectively in the process of diluted education applications; in the distance education process, they used demonstration method and reduced the number of activities and examples. According to the study findings, it was concluded that inclusive educational environments, which are based on students' fair use of all educational opportunities, could not be provided especially in distance education environments carried out during the pandemic process.

Keywords: Diluted Education, Distance Education, Inclusive Education, Phenomenology Study.

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1. Introduction

Epidemic diseases are important situations that affect human history. The nature of epidemic diseases and ways to protect them and their treatments were not fully known for a long time. This affects people's lives and indirectly affects their educational status. The whole world has witnessed this recently.

The Covid-19 virus began to spread from Wuhan, China in late 2019, threatening the lives of people all over the world (Hui et al., 2020, p. 264). Labeled as a "pandemic" by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11 March, coronavirus is estimated to have affected the educational lives of more than 1.5 billion students and 63 million educators (UNESCO, 2020). In most countries, schools were closed and education was provided through distance

learning platforms (Reimers, 2020). Recent modeling studies of COVID-19 predict that school closures alone will prevent only 2-4% of the losses caused by the virus (Viner et al., 2020). For this reason, country governments have taken measures such as social distancing, travel bans and subsequent curfews to slow the spread of the Covid-19 virus (OECD, 2020). In these circumstances, education, which is part of the daily lives of millions of students and teachers, has been greatly affected around the world (Hopegood; 2020; Saavedra, 2020).

Schools in Turkey decided to close on March 16, 2020, and MoNE strengthened the infrastructure of the Education Information Network (EBA), which serves as a digital education platform, in order to establish an effective distance education system. In order to prevent problems that may arise due to overloading the system, which classes should use EBA and at which time intervals were planned and students were informed. As of March 23, a cooperation was established with the Turkish Radio and Television Corporation (TRT), enabling children to follow their lessons on TRT EBA TV. A hotline was also established to support the psychological welfare of students and parents. In addition, 8GB free internet service was provided for students to access EBA. In addition, after pilot studies were carried out for the live classroom application with the 8th and 12th grades, live lessons were made widespread throughout the country (Özer, 2020).

Table 1: Weekly course schedule to be applied in face-to-face education during the Covid-19 epidemic in the 2020-2021 academic year

LESSONS	FACE TO FACE EDUCATION CLASS				FACE TO FACE EDUCATION CLASS			
	HOURS				HOURS			
	DAY 1				DAY 2			
	1st Grade	2nd Grade	3rd Grade	4th Grade	1st Grade	2nd Grade	3rd Grade	4th Grade
Turkish	4	3	3	3	4	3	3	2
Maths	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1
Life Science	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	1
Science	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1
Foreign Language	-	1	1	1	-	-	-	-
Religious Culture and Moral Knowledge	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1
Total	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6

In Türkiye, face-to-face education and distance education applications were used together starting from September 2020. In Turkey, education was conducted in diluted classrooms with face-to-face education two days a week and distance education one day a week. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the class size was divided into two in order to continue face-to-face education activities in a diluted manner. The first group of the class was divided into two groups and received face-to-face education on Mondays and Tuesdays, while the second group received face-to-face education on Thursdays and Fridays. On Wednesday, face-to-face education was interrupted and a day was set aside for cleaning the school. In addition, the entire class received six hours of distance education on Wednesday. The duration of the lessons was reduced to 30 minutes, and in addition to

the duration of the lessons, the class hours were reduced from 30 hours to 15 hours per week (MoNE, 2021).

The pandemic has greatly affected education, which is a part of the daily lives of billions of students and teachers almost everywhere in the world (Hopegood, 2020). It is emphasized that the measures taken to slow down the spread of the disease during the Covid-19 pandemic and the practices carried out as an alternative to face-to-face education will increase the existing inequalities in the education system, may have longer-term consequences for those who have been discriminated against, who may be exposed to economic difficulties and stress as well as unavailable learning opportunities (Giannini & Lewis, 2020). In addition, Giannini and Albrechtsen (2020) state that it will have devastating effects on girls and disadvantaged students, especially in low socio-economic regions.

During the pandemic, diluted classroom practices that allow for face-to-face education and learning practices that are a blend of distance education have been tried for the first time in our country and in other countries of the world, especially at the primary school level, and their effects and results on education can only be evaluated with the experiences obtained at the end of this process. Practices carried out in educational environments have also been affected by this process. One of these practices is inclusive education practices.

In a very basic and simple way, inclusive education is a fundamental right where everyone has access to education and is not discriminated (Altunoğlu, 2019). Inclusive education is a process that provides every child of school age with the opportunity to receive quality education in educational environments. It emphasizes the right of all children to be educated with other children of their own age and with their peers in regular/regular classes and to attend these schools (Uchem and Ngwa, 2014). In the Salamanca Declaration, inclusive education is defined as "the process of addressing and meeting the diversity of needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning, cultures and communities and reducing exclusion in education" (UNESCO, 1994).

As it can be seen, there is no study that examines diluted and distance education practices together in the context of inclusion. Based on this need, this study aims to evaluate the diluted and distance education practices at the primary school level in Türkiye in the context of inclusive education according to teachers' views. In line with this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

1. What kind of teaching strategies did teachers use in diluted and distance education practices and what did they pay attention to when choosing these strategies?
2. What kind of materials did teachers use during diluted and distance education practices and what was taken into consideration in the selection of the materials used?
3. What has been done to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process in diluted and distance education practices?
4. What kind of arrangements have been made for disadvantaged students in diluted and distance education practices?

2. Method

This study, which was designed with qualitative research method, is a phenomenology study. The phenomenological design focuses on phenomena that we are aware of but do not have a detailed and in-depth understanding. (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016 p.72). The study group of the study consists of 7 primary school teachers working in Gaziantep province in the 2020-2021 academic year. In determining the participants, in line with the criterion sampling method, it was aimed to reach classroom teachers working at different grade levels, whose years of service were not less than five years. The study group is small because it is formed for the purpose (Baker et al., 1992; Morse, 2000; Starks & Trinidad, 2007).

The teachers participating in the research were given code names as Teacher1, Teacher2, Teacher3, and these code names were abbreviated as T1, T2, T3. The demographic characteristics of the teachers participating in the research are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the teachers participating in the research

<i>Gender</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Education Level</i>	<i>N</i>
Woman	3(T2,T3,T4,)	Bachelor	6
Male	4(T1,T5,T6,T7)	Postgraduate	1(T1)
Total	7	Total	7
<i>Grade Level</i>		<i>Professional Year</i>	
1st Grade	3 (T2,T3,T4)	0-5 years	1(T7)
2nd Grade	2(T6,T7)	6-10 years	1 (T3)
3rd Grade	1(T5)	11-15 years	5 (T1,T2,T4,T5,T6)
4th Grade	1(T1)	15+ years	-
Total	7	Total	7

Of the 7 classroom teachers in the study group, 4 were male and 3 were female. While 3 of the classroom teachers in the study group were first grade teachers, 2 of them were second grade teachers, one was a third grade teacher and one was a fourth grade teacher. While 6 of the teachers had undergraduate education, one of them had postgraduate education. Five of the teachers had a professional seniority of 11-15 years, one had a professional seniority of 6-10 years and one had a professional seniority of 5 years. Shows the number of mainstreaming and foreign students of the teachers participating in the study. All of the teachers participating in the study had foreign students in their classes, and 5 of them had mainstreaming students in their classes.

A semi-structured interview form developed by the researchers was used in the study. The interview form consists of 12 open-ended questions. After the interview questions were prepared by the researchers, they were presented to two field experts and necessary arrangements were made. The interview method has many advantages. (Çepni, 2009; Glesne, 2013). Since the study was conducted during the Covid-19 pandemic, interviews were conducted using electronic communication tools and Zoom program. At this stage, the interview audio recordings were first transcribed into text format. The data obtained from the study was analyzed by content analysis method. Content analysis, which is frequently used in qualitative research, can be defined as a repeatable and systematic

technique in which some words of a text are summarized by coding into smaller categories (Büyüköztürk et al. 2013).

This study was conducted with the ethics committee decision of Anadolu University Social Sciences and Humanities Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Committee dated 27.04.2021 and numbered 60372. Ethical principles and publication ethics were complied with during the research process.

In this study, 30% of the data obtained as a result of semi-structured interviews analyzed and coded independently by the researchers and the expert. There was consensus between the researcher and the expert on all of the feedback. As a result of the reliability calculations, an agreement rate above 0.70 is considered reliable for the research (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

3. Findings

In this section, the findings related to the research questions are presented through tables, explanations and direct quotations. This question was analyzed in two sub-themes: what is considered when dividing the class into two groups and the teaching methods used. The findings of the teachers' opinions on the points they paid attention to when dividing the class into two groups are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Findings regarding the points taken into consideration when dividing the class into two groups

<i>Code</i>	<i>N</i>
Academic success	4
According to participation in the live lesson	3
Total	7

While 4 of the teachers participating in the research stated that they took into account the academic achievement of the students while dividing the class into two groups in diluted education practices, 3 of them stated that they formed groups according to the students' participation in the live lesson. The teachers participating in the study expressed the points they took into account when dividing the class into two groups in diluted education practices as follows:

Teacher2: When the school started in the second semester, I transferred my students who had already started reading and writing to the Monday-Tuesday group, that is, to the first group. I took my students who could not read and write to the Thursday-Friday group (academic success).

Teacher5: While dividing the class into two groups, I divided the class into two groups: students who participated in distance education and those who did not (participation in the live lesson).

The findings reflecting the opinions of the teachers participating in the research regarding the teaching methods used in diluted and distance education applications are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Teaching methods used in diluted and distance education applications

<i>Teaching methods used in diluted education practices</i>	
Code	N
Show and tell	5
Question-answer	2
Lecture	2
Problem solving	1
Total	9
<i>Teaching methods used in distance education applications</i>	
Code	N
Show and tell	5
Reducing activities and examples	2
Using musical games	1
No effect on methods	1
Total	9

The teachers participating in the study stated that they used demonstration (n=5), question-answer (n=2), lecture (n=2) and problem solving (n=1) methods during the diluted education practices. In the distance education process, they stated that they preferred the demonstration method (n=5) and reduced the number of activities and examples (n=2). In addition, they stated that they used musical games (n=2) and had no effect on the methods (n=1). Excerpts from their statements regarding the teaching methods they used in diluted education are as follows:

Teacher1: Since I teach literacy, I showed it and the students read and wrote... (Show and tell)

Teacher5: We, as the teacher, took the center stage and tried to give the essence of the subject as much as possible... (Lecture)

Teacher7: ...I switched from student-centered activities to lecture and demonstration method because I had time problems... (Direct explanation and demonstration)

Teacher3: ...I frequently used the question-answer method in order to use the time effectively...(Question-answer)

Excerpts from the statements of the teachers participating in the research regarding the teaching methods they use in distance education are as follows:

Teacher1:... without involving students in the lesson... instead of explaining a topic with ten examples, I explained it with one example... (Reducing activities and examples)

Teacher3:...the method I use the most is music, that is, when his attention falls, I play music and play a game immediately. (Using musical games)

The findings reflecting the views of the teachers participating in the study on the course materials used in the diluted and distance education applications are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Findings regarding course materials used in diluted and distance education applications

<i>Course materials used in diluted educational practices</i>	
Code	N
Educational materials that are ready/prepared by the teacher	3
Enables effective use of time	2
Students' inability to participate in material production	2
Selection of accessible (printed) materials	2
Selection of material with a large number of questions	1
Increasing resource diversity	1
Total	10
<i>Course materials used in distance education applications</i>	
Code	N
Using visual and audio materials	3
Using home equipment in class	2
Making materials with parent support	2
Using printed materials such as textbooks and workbooks	1
Using worksheets with screen sharing	1
Total	9

The teachers who participated in the study stated that they preferred to use ready-made or self-prepared (n=3), time-efficient (n=2), accessible (printed) teaching materials (n=2) and that students could not participate in material production (n=2). In addition, they stated that they tended to choose materials with more questions (n=2) and that the variety of resources increased (n=1). The teachers who participated in the study stated that they used audio-visual materials (n=3) and home materials (n=2), made materials with the support of parents (n=2), used printed materials such as textbooks and workbooks (n=1) and used worksheets with screen sharing (n=1). The teachers participating in the study expressed their views on the course materials they used in diluted education practices in the following sentences:

Teacher 4: ...I drew shapes... For example, I made a frog. I created a material that would make a word every time it pulled its tongue out of its mouth. But since they are not going to be able to prepare it in a short time, I had to prepare it, I could have had the children do it... Actually in the classroom I like to do it more with the children. But during this period, we did not have the chance to spend time with one child because they were at school for just two days...

(Educational materials that are ready/prepared by the teacher, Students cannot participate in material production, Ensuring effective use of time)

Teacher 7:... While I was previously using materials based on learning by doing, I turned to printed materials because time was limited... (Accessible (printed) material selection)

Teacher 2: ...As materials, we used more than one material; we used school books and the resource books we received... The resources we use have diversified, we send homework from the internet. As much as the children can access them, so not everyone can print out the homework I send them. In terms of reaching them, I can say that the assignments I sent and the resources are on the internet... I also looked to see if there was

a test question for children to self-evaluate once they understood the topic.... (Accessible (printed) material selection, increasing resource diversity)

Excerpts from their statements regarding the course materials used in distance education applications are as follows:

Teacher 5: I used only visual and audio materials as materials. Unfortunately, materials that children could make themselves by participating in the process could not be used. (Using visual and audio materials)

Teacher 4: Whatever we have at home, some of the materials that children have at home... I told them to use jars for decimals for example. (Using tools and materials at home in the lesson)

Teacher 3:... While we were studying the clock topic, we used to make clocks in the classroom, but now we have parents make them at home... (Making materials with parent support)

Teacher 1:...I can share the content on the screen, especially the worksheets... (Using worksheets with screen sharing)

The findings reflecting the views of the teachers participating in the research on what is done to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Findings regarding what is done to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process

<i>Actions taken to participate in the diluted education process</i>	
Code	N
Communication and cooperation with parents	6
Organizing lessons according to the child's age and interests	2
Adopting an explanation from easy to difficult	1
Total	8
<i>Things done to participate in live classes during the distance education process</i>	
Code	N
Communication and cooperation with parents	6
Planning in a way that does not conflict with other siblings	2
Using student-centered methods	2
Using musical games	1
Spanning the course over two days	1
Adopting an explanation from easy to difficult	1
Total	13

The teachers who participated in the study stated that they tried to ensure communication and cooperation with parents in order to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process in diluted education (n=6), organized the lessons according to the age and interest of the child (n=2) and adopted an easy-to-difficult narrative (n=1). In order to ensure the participation of students in the learning-teaching process in live lessons in the distance education process, they stated that they tried to ensure communication and cooperation with parents (n=6), made planning so as not to overlap with other siblings (n=2), used student-centered methods (n=2), used musical games (n=1), spread the lesson

over two days (n=1) and adopted an easy-to-difficult expression (n=1). The teachers who participated in the study expressed their views on what was done to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process in diluted education with the following sentences:

Teacher 1: Since the students' levels were very different and so that they could experience the feeling of success, I followed an explanation from easy to difficult. I asked students questions according to their level... (adopting an explanation from easy to difficult)

The teachers who participated in the study expressed their views on what was done to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process in distance education with the following sentences:

Teacher 6: We met with parents, held remote meetings... (communication and cooperation with parents)

Teacher 7: I mostly used methods and strategies that centered on students. (using student-centered methods)

Teacher 5:...there is a curfew on Saturdays and Sundays, so I continued the process by spreading it out like this... I try to address both groups as much as I can... It prevents overlapping with siblings... (planning in a way that does not overlap with other siblings)

The findings reflecting the views of the teachers participating in the research on the practices with disadvantaged students in the process of diluted education and distance education are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Findings regarding the practices carried out with disadvantaged students in the diluted and distance education process

<i>Practices with disadvantaged students in the process of diluted education</i>	
Code	N
Providing the opportunity for one-on-one attention and follow-up due to the decrease in class size	3
Students who cannot participate in distance education not participating in face to face education.	3
Creating a distinction between those who attend the live lessons and those who cannot attend	2
Complete lack of communication especially with refugee students due to lack of access to technological communication tools	2
The negative impact of coming to school for two days on student success	2
Total	12
<i>Practices with disadvantaged students during distance education</i>	
Code	N
Not making any arrangements because disadvantaged students cannot participate in the course	3
Since only 1-2 disadvantaged students attended the class and there were art, music and physical education classes, no arrangements were made	3
Trying to ensure their participation in the lesson with easy to difficult explanations.	1
Total	7

Regarding the practices with disadvantaged students in the diluted education process, the teachers who participated in the research stated that they had the opportunity

to deal with and follow up one-on-one with the decrease in class size (n=3), and that students who could not participate in distance education did not participate in face-to-face education (n=3), They stated that distance education created a distinction between those who could and could not participate in live classes (n=2), that communication was completely lost especially with refugee students due to lack of access to technological communication tools (n=2), and that coming to school for two days had a negative impact on student achievement (n=1). Regarding the arrangements made for disadvantaged students in live lessons, the teachers who participated in the study stated that they did not make any arrangements because disadvantaged students could not participate in the lesson (n=3), because only 1-2 disadvantaged students participated in the lesson (n=2) or because there were art, physical education and music lessons (n=1), and that they tried to ensure their participation in the lesson with an easy to difficult expression (n=1). The teachers who participated in the study expressed their views on the practices with disadvantaged students in the diluted education process in the following sentences:

Teacher4: ..we had more chances to deal with the children one-on-one... (reduced class size, giving the opportunity for one-on-one care and follow-up)

Teacher5:...children with good facilities, children with poor facilities, or children with devices who can or cannot connect to the internet...a very clear distinction emerged... students who could not participate in distance education did not want to participate in face-to-face education...(students who could not participate in distance education did not participate in face-to-face education)

Teacher7: The practices we carried out in this context were completely discontinued due to the student's inability to use communication channels (especially with refugee students due to the lack of access to technological communication tools).

Teacher3:...Unfortunately, two days was not enough for these students...(the negative impact of coming to school for two days on student success)

The teachers who participated in the study expressed their views on the arrangements made for disadvantaged students in live lessons in distance education with the following sentences:

Teacher2: I did not make any arrangements because these students could not participate in the lesson (not making any arrangements because disadvantaged students could not participate in the lesson)

Teacher3: Only one of my students attends the class, I make the same arrangements as the others (since only 1-2 disadvantaged students attend the class and there are art, music and physical education classes, I do not make any arrangements)

Teacher6: On Wednesday, we did not feel the need to make any arrangements because we only had art, physical education and music classes (no arrangements were made because only 1-2 disadvantaged students attended the class and there were art, music and physical education classes).

Teacher1: ...I progressed from easy to difficult so that the student could experience the feeling of success... (trying to ensure their participation in the lesson by explaining from easy to difficult)

The findings reflecting the views of the participating teachers on the advantages and limitations of diluted education practices for children with disadvantages are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Findings on the advantages and limitations of diluted education practices

<i>Advantages of Diluted Education</i>	<i>N</i>
Class size halved	3
Necessity for cleanliness/health	2
Shortening the course duration	2
Total	7
<i>Limitations of Diluted Education</i>	<i>N</i>
No changes to the training program	3
Disengagement of students from education	2
Absence of those who cannot participate in distance education	2
Short time spent at school	2
Long time spent at home	2
Increasing individual differences	2
Shortening the course duration	2
Processing only pivotal courses	1
Students getting bored of the same lessons	1
Total	17

The teachers who participated in the study stated the halving of the class size (n=3), cleanliness/health necessity (n=2), and shortening the duration of the course (n=2) as the advantages of diluted education. The teachers who participated in the study stated that no changes were made in the education program (n=3), students' disconnection/removal from education (n=2), absenteeism of those who could not participate in distance education (n=2), short time spent at school (n=2). The teachers who participated in the study expressed the following as the limitations of diluted education: long time spent at home (n=2), increase in individual differences (n=2), shortening of the lesson duration (n=2), teaching only the center lessons (n=1) and students getting bored with the same lessons (n=1). The teachers participating in the study expressed their views on the advantages and limitations of diluted education in the following sentences:

Teacher4: Our biggest advantage was halving the class size. We have more chances to deal with the children one-on-one...In general, it was actually very good in terms of health. We were coming two, four days every two weeks. One day, the school had cleaning... (class size halved, necessity for cleanliness/health)

Teacher1: Too long an interval causes children to forget and drift away from school. I think this is the biggest factor, as a negative... (short time spent at school)

Teacher2: In order to complete the curriculum, lessons are given in the form of Turkish, mathematics, science and life sciences...Not being able to do painting, music, PE, etc.; it is a disadvantage for me that the children get bored and cannot do these things by

having them do the same lessons all the time... (teaching only the main lessons, students getting bored with the same lessons)

4. Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, which aims to evaluate the diluted and distance education practices carried out at the primary school level in Turkey during the Covid-19 pandemic according to teachers' views in the context of inclusive education, it was found that in diluted education practices; while dividing the class into two groups, teachers consider academic achievement and live class participation and therefore prefer to create a homogeneous classroom environment. Mutlu, Öztürk, and Aytekin (2019) stated that the "one-size-fits-all" approach continues to be applied in many classrooms today; mostly standard learning resources are used, and emphasized that teachers should change their teaching approaches to meet the educational needs of students in heterogeneous classroom environments. In the traditional educational approach, it is assumed that all individuals have the same characteristics and therefore learning activities are carried out accordingly (Rollins, 2011). In this study, it was observed that teachers did not prefer teaching approaches to provide education in a heterogeneous classroom. One of the reasons for this may be that teachers who adopt a traditional educational approach think that there is only one way to learn (Dunn & Dunn, 1992). The understanding of inclusive education, which is one of the contemporary educational approaches, is that students receive qualified education appropriate to their characteristics in heterogeneous groups with their peers. Therefore, it can be said that the teachers participating in the study did not prefer an educational environment suitable for the nature of inclusive education.

The teachers who participated in the study stated that they used demonstration, question-answer, lecture and problem solving methods and techniques in the diluted education applications process. In the distance education process, on the other hand, they stated that they used the demonstration method, reduced the number of activities and examples, and used musical games. It is seen that the teachers participating in the study mostly used similar methods and techniques in face-to-face and distance education processes. In Arslan's (2021) study with preschool teachers, it was found that teachers could include more activities in face-to-face education, while distance education limited the activities. In their studies conducted with science teachers by Bakioğlu and Çevik (2020) and classroom teachers by Şahan and Parlar (2021), it was stated that teachers mostly conducted lessons with questions and answers, ready-made videos and slides during the distance education process. These findings coincide with the study. Keskin, Şentürk, Ömer, and Dursun (2021) stated in their study that the methods and techniques used in the face-to-face education process in social studies courses could not be used in distance education courses. Bakioğlu and Çevik (2020), in their study of science teachers, concluded that lecture and question-answer methods and techniques were used in distance education. Avcı and Akdeniz (2021), on the other hand, stated that a limited part of the activities carried out in face-to-face education can be done in the distance education process. Although these findings are similar to the results of the study, they do not completely overlap. When the study findings and other studies in the literature are examined, it is seen that the distance education process brings limitations in terms of teaching methods.

However, it is seen that differentiated, collaborative, individualized teaching methods (Altunoğlu, 2019), which are recommended to be used in the inclusive education approach in the face-to-face education process carried out with students in diluted education practices, are not used at all. Basing the teaching process on classical teaching methods interrupts students' experiences based on cooperation and sharing (Yıldırım, 2020). Therefore, it can be said that face-to-face lessons in diluted education practices are not carried out in accordance with the inclusive education approach.

As a result of the study, it was concluded that teachers preferred ready-made/teacher-prepared educational materials as course materials during diluted education practices. In distance education applications, on the other hand, it was observed that they preferred to use visual and auditory materials. Bakioğlu and Çevik (2020) found that science teachers preferred documents such as books and essays more in the distance education process. Kavuk and Demirtaş (2021) stated that there are difficulties in the use of teaching materials in their studies. Mengi and Alpdoğan (2020) concluded that the instructional materials used in the distance education process were not effective for students who could not gain the ability to access information and could not receive family support. Reich et al. (2020), in their study providing guidance for distance education studies covering 50 states in the United States, stated that schools should find non-digital alternatives using public television, print, or other approaches, considering that many families cannot access online options in accordance with the principle of equity and access. Materials are the tools that enable students to concretize knowledge, to reach achievements by doing and experiencing; in summary, they are the tools that support teaching (Özyürek, 1983). In the light of the findings obtained as a result of the research and the studies in the literature, it is seen that the diversity of materials used in distance education and diluted education applications has not been ensured. It can be said that the decrease in the diversity of learning materials during the pandemic process and the limitations in accessing these materials cause learning deficiencies in students.

As a result of the study, it is noteworthy that teachers did not express the educational information network as the most important source in providing content and materials to teachers in the distance education process. When the studies on EBA are examined in the literature, there are studies on the inadequacy of the content and infrastructure. For example, Kurt, Kuzu, Dursun, Güllüpinar, and Gültekin (2013) found in their study that teachers had problems with content, especially in the distance education process. Demirçelik (2019) mentioned the problems arising from the insufficiency of infrastructure and content in his study. Altın and Kalelioğlu (2015) concluded that the number of materials in the educational information network was not sufficient. Although these studies do not fully overlap with the study findings, they show similarities. These studies show that the content problems of the educational information network date back to before the pandemic (Akıncı, Kurtoğlu and Seferoğlu, 2012: Güven, 2012: Ekici and Yılmaz, 2013: Özkan and Demir, 2014: Ateş, Çerçi and Derman, 2015: Kayahan and Özduvan, 2016: Tüysüz and Çimen, 2016: Saklan, 2017).

As a result of this study, it was found that teachers mostly tried to communicate and cooperate with parents in order to ensure students' participation in the learning-teaching process. However, it was found that no arrangements were made because disadvantaged

students could not participate in the lesson and students who could not participate in distance education did not participate in diluted education. The long time spent at home during the diluted education practices and the inability of students to participate in distance education will cause learning losses. It is expected that the pandemic process will cause learning losses in mathematics and reading skills, especially in younger students, and that students will start school with high levels of learning losses (Wyse, Stickney, Butz, Beckler, & Close, 2020; Kuhfeld, Soland, Tarasawa, Johnson, Ruzek, & Liu, 2020). In the pandemic, the transition from face-to-face education to distance education has been a difficult process for underprivileged students and disadvantaged groups (Tremmel et al., 2020; Giannini & Albrechtsen, 2020). Saygı (2021) and Alea, Fabrea, Roldan, & Farooqi (2020) concluded that the participation rate in distance education live courses is insufficient. Yıldız and Akar Vural (2020) concluded in their study that children with chronic diseases and children in need of special education could not access educational opportunities sufficiently during the pandemic period; in addition, students whose mother tongue is not Turkish, asylum-seeker families and seasonal workers' children could not benefit equally from distance education. Dube (2020) concluded that the South African government promoted online learning as the only alternative in the context of Covid-19, but ignored the education of many learners in rural areas who could not connect to the internet due to lack of resources. It has been observed that many students living in rural areas of China, which has been greatly affected by the pandemic and implemented distance education activities in this process, do not have the equipment or connection to participate in distance education. They had problems benefiting from the distance education system due to inadequacies or inconveniences in the home environment (such as households living together) (Lau, Yang, & Dasgupta, 2020). There are studies that concluded that the inability to ensure equal opportunity in education during the pandemic process is among the leading problems (Can & Günbayı, 2021; Çelik & İşler, 2020; Kabapınar, Kanyılmaz, Ören Koçhan, & Atik, 2021). In its report, TEDMEM (2020) reveals that teachers and students have communication problems and that distance education is not efficient enough for students who cannot create their own study system. In their research, Sönmez, Yıldırım, and Çetinkaya (2020) found that distance education during the pandemic was greatly affected by the socioeconomic status of families. According to the study findings, it can be said that inclusive educational environments, which are based on students' fair use of all educational opportunities regardless of differences such as language, religion, race, age, gender, socio-economic level or social class, cannot be provided especially in distance education environments carried out during the pandemic process. In this sense, the result reached in the study coincides with other studies conducted in the literature.

In this study, it was found that diluted education has a positive effect on the practices with disadvantaged students, such as reducing the class size and giving the opportunity to deal with and follow up one-to-one. Giannini and Albrechtsen (2020) stated that the pandemic will have devastating effects especially on disadvantaged students. In the education of students with special needs, such as mainstreamed students and gifted and talented students, individualized education programs (IEPs) are needed to respond to their needs. IEP is prepared by considering the individual differences of the student with special needs (Martin, Van Dycke, Christensen Greene, Gardner, & Lovett, 2006). In the literature, there are studies showing that there are problems in the implementation of IEP due to

crowded classrooms and inappropriate physical conditions (Tekin Ersan & Ata, 2016; Gök & Erbaş, 2011). Based on this finding, it can be thought that teachers implement individualized education programs more effectively in the process of diluted education practices.

5. References

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